

PECHMANN'S CONDENSATION OF METHYL β -RESORCYLATE AND β -RESORCYLIC ACID WITH ETHYL ACETOACETATE.

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Clayton generalised that negative substituents like nitro, carboxyl and carbethoxyl inhibit Pechmann's coumarin-condensation. 2-Nitro- and 4-nitroresorcinols, however, readily condense with ethyl acetoacetate (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622; Chakravarti and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 37).

We find that methyl β -resorcylicate and β -resorcylic acid smoothly condense with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of sulphuric acid, the former giving a mixture of methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate and the corresponding carboxylic acid and the latter the free acid. The constitutions of the acid and the ester follow from the decarboxylation of the acid to known 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.

The condensation of methyl β -resorcylicate was also carried out with phosphoryl chloride, phosphoric anhydride and hydrogen chloride as condensing agents, the same coumarin ester being obtained in low yields. It is noteworthy that the condensation proceeds differently in the presence of aluminium chloride the main product being a 5-hydroxy-coumarin, methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *Current Science*, 1937, 6, 94).

β -Resorcylic acid also condenses with malic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid with the formation of 7-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (*cf.* Arima, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1929, 4, 113). Methyl β -resorcylicate gives the same acid, the ester being completely hydrolysed at the temperature required for the condensation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate and 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.

Concentrated sulphuric acid (80%, 30 c. c.) was added to a mixture of methyl β -resorcylicate (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4.5 g.). The mixture

after standing overnight, was added to cold water. The yellowish solid (7.8 g.) was collected, washed with water and then treated with excess of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The insoluble solid consisting of the coumarin ester was filtered and the filtrate was acidified when the free acid was precipitated as a granular solid.

The coumarin ester crystallised from alcohol in shining colourless needles, m. p. $212-14^{\circ}$, yield 3 g. (Found : C, 61.6; H, 4.3. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.5; H, 4.3 per cent). The ester is moderately soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, acetone and chloroform, but very sparingly in benzene and water. It gives a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in caustic soda with difficulty, the alkaline solution having a strong blue fluorescence.

The acetyl derivative, prepared by refluxing the ester (0.3 g.) with acetic anhydride (1 c. c.) and 2-3 drops of pyridine for 2 hours, crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m. p. $171-73^{\circ}$, yield 0.15 g. (Found : C, 60.6; H, 4.4. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 60.9; H, 4.3 per cent).

The benzoyl derivative, prepared by heating with benzoyl chloride for 1 hour at 100° in pyridine solution, crystallised from hot xylene in shining buttons, m. p. $173-74^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 67.3; H, 4.2. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.4; H, 4.2 per cent).

The methyl ether was prepared by refluxing for 20 hours the ester (0.5 g.) dissolved in acetone (50 c. c.), fused potassium carbonate (1 g.) and methyl iodide (3 c. c.). It was crystallised from rectified spirit as clusters of tiny needles, m. p. $186-88^{\circ}$, yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 62.82; H, 4.95. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.83 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali and does not give a ferric chloride colouration.

The coumarin acid crystallised from alcohol in short faintly coloured needles, m. p. $284-85^{\circ}$, yield 2 g. (Found : C, 59.8; H, 3.7. $C_{11}H_8O_5$ requires C, 60.0; H, 3.6 per cent). It is only sparingly soluble in alcohol and the alcoholic solution gives a dark violet colouration with ferric chloride. It dissolves in alkali to a pale yellow solution with intense blue fluorescence. Attempts to prepare acetyl and benzoyl derivatives by the usual methods were unsuccessful.

The same acid was obtained by the hydrolysis of the coumarin ester preferably by cold alkali. 0.5 G. of the ester was kept in contact with caustic soda solution (20 c. c., 10 %) for 3 days when the ester went completely into solution. Acidification yielded the acid, identical with the acid described above. The acid was also obtained by hydrolysis with boiling acetic acid—hydrochloric acid or hot acetic acid—sulphuric acid or cold concentrated sulphuric acid.

Decarboxylation of 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The acid (0.4 g.) and water (25 c.c.) were heated together in a sealed tube at 180° for 7 hours. The decarboxylated product, which had separated in thin shining needles with a brownish tinge, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 185-86°, not depressed by admixture with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, yield quantitative. The acid can also be conveniently decarboxylated by gently heating the substance in a test tube, until effervescence ceases.

Condensation of β -Resorcylic Acid with Ethyl Acetoacetate.—Concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) was added to a mixture of β -resorcylic acid (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) when heat was evolved and the mixture turned brownish. After keeping overnight, the mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours, cooled and poured into water. The precipitated solid was treated with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution when most of it dissolved, leaving a small amount of residue which when crystallised from alcohol had m.p. 185-86° and was found to be 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin. The sodium bicarbonate extract on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid, gave a yellowish coloured precipitate, which was collected and crystallised from alcohol or glacial acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 284-85° identical with the acid described above, yield 1.5 g.

Condensation of Methyl β -Resorcyate with Ethyl Acetoacetate in presence of (i) Phosphoryl chloride (ii) Phosphoric anhydride and (iii) Hydrogen chloride.

(i) To a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (4 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (3.5 g.) phosphorus oxychloride (7 g.) was added and the reaction mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. Water was added to the brown pasty mass. On keeping overnight in a frigidaire dark-brown semi-solid mass was obtained. This was dissolved in rectified spirit (charcoal). On keeping black tarry mass came down which was rejected. The clear solution was then concentrated and kept in a frigidaire when faint yellow coloured needles separated, m.p. and mixed n.p. with the compound prepared by using sulphuric acid, 212-14°, yield 0.3 g.

(ii) Methyl β -resorcyate (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4.5 g.) were mixed together and phosphorus pentoxide (5 g.) added. The reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for about 45 minutes. On cooling water was added and the semi-solid mass obtained crystallised from rectified spirit as needles, m.p. and

mixed m.p. with the compound prepared by sulphuric acid method, 212-14°, yield about 0.2 g.

(iii) Methyl β -resorcylate (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4.5 g.) were dissolved in sufficient cold absolute alcohol and dry hydrochloric acid gas passed through the cooled solution for 2½ hours. It was then left overnight when white needles separated. Water was added to precipitate the product completely which was then crystallised from rectified spirit colourless shining needles, m.p. and mixed m. p. with the compound prepared by sulphuric acid method, 212-14°, yield 1.3 g.

7-Hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—Concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) was added to a mixture of β -resorcylate (5 g.) and malic acid (4.5 g.) and the mixture left overnight. After heating at 100° for 3-4 hours, it was poured into water. The pasty mass, which separated, solidified on keeping overnight in a frigidaire. It crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 268°-69°. Arima (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 244°-260° according to rate of heating. (Found: C, 53.4; H, 3.5. Calc. for $C_{10}H_6O_5$, H_2O : C, 53.6; H, 3.4 per cent).

The acid dissolves in sodium bicarbonate forming a sparingly soluble sodium salt which immediately separates. It dissolves in alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid with a strong blue fluorescence.

The acid on decarboxylation by gentle heating gave 7-hydroxy coumarin, identified by direct comparison with an authentic specimen. The same acid was obtained by keeping a mixture of methyl β -resorcylate (5 g.), malic acid (4.2 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) overnight, and then heating at 100° for 2 hours.

The analyses recorded are micro-analyses by Dr. Schoeller.

Further work on the condensation of other phenol-carboxylic acids and their esters with β -ketonic esters is being carried out by two of the authors (R.C.S. and S.M.S.).

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